

Electrical Conductivity of Acetylcholine Halides and Perchlorate in 2-Propanol at 25°

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Studies on electrolytic conductance of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate solutions in water, methanol, ethanol and n-propanol at 25°, have been reported recently^{1,2}. The present communication reports a precise study of the conductance of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in 2-propanol at 25° in order to throw light on the behaviour of these salts in branched simple solvents.

Results and Discussion

The measured equivalent conductance data are shown in Table 1. An approximate value of Λ_0 was estimated from Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ plot.

More accurate values of Λ_0 were estimated from the Fuoss-Kraus-Shedlovsky equation³,

$$1/\Lambda S_{(z)} = 1/\Lambda_0 + (CA S_{(z)} f^2) K_D \Lambda^2$$

where K_D is the dissociation constant and $S_{(z)}$ the Shedlovsky's function which was tabulated by Daggett⁴ for different values of z . The value of z can be calculated from the equation,

$$z = (\alpha/\Lambda_0^{3/2})(CA)^{1/2}$$

in which α is the limiting tangent.

The plot of $1/\Lambda S_{(z)}$ vs $(CA S_{(z)} f^2)$ gives $1/\Lambda_0$ as intercept and $1/K_D \Lambda_0^2$ as slope. Fig. 1 illustrates the (FKS) plots for the studied salts.

The true values of Λ_0 , a^0 and K_A were derived using Fuoss-Onsager equation⁵ and starting by the value of Λ_0 which was obtained from (FKS)

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE OF ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN 2-PROPANOL AT 25°

Chloride		Bromide		Iodide		Perchlorate	
$10^4 C$	Λ	$10^4 C$	L	$10^4 C$	Λ	$10^4 C$	Λ
16.649	14.75	8.478	16.15	5.340	17.50	8.828	17.59
13.904	15.37	7.405	16.65	4.439	17.95	8.117	17.78
12.134	15.75	6.906	16.77	3.729	18.83	7.488	18.19
10.631	16.20	6.499	16.97	3.194	19.04	6.920	18.61
9.552	16.48	5.805	17.35	2.737	19.51	6.191	19.00
8.447	16.80	5.117	17.66			5.456	19.50
		4.723	17.93				

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC PARAMETERS FOR ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN 2-PROPANOL AT 25° (DERIVED FROM FUOSS-ONSAGER EQUATION)

Salt	Λ_0	J	a^0	K_A	αA
Ac.Cl	22.89 ± 0.81	1994.5	6.92 ± 0.10	460.37 ± 3.12	0.57
Ac.Br	23.35 ± 0.45	1986.2	6.45 ± 0.11	670.03 ± 5.13	0.05
Ac.I	24.41 ± 0.51	1899.5	5.24 ± 0.10	935.50 ± 8.15	0.21
Ac.ClO ₄	27.93 ± 0.53	1882.6	4.48 ± 0.10	1051.80 ± 11.78	0.10

equation³. In our calculations a computer program on an IBM-PC machine was used. The accuracies required in these computations are ± 0.02 for Λ_0 , ± 2 for $J < 200$; ± 5 for $J = 200-1000$, and ± 10 for $J > 1000$. The derived constants are represented in Table 2.

Table 2 reveals that Λ_0 increases from acetylcholine Cl^- to ClO_4^- according to the ionic equivalent conductance of anions. The values of J and a^0 decrease with increasing the size of anions. This supports the opinion⁶ that for salts with common cation, the size of the anion becomes the essential factor in controlling the extent of ion-pairing. The solvation of these anions of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate increases in the direction $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which is in accordance with the trend of a^0 . From electrostatic point of view, since the distance between the cation and the anion increases in the same order, the forces of attraction increase in the order, $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$. In our case the trend is that K_A increases with the increase of the size of anions.

Matesich *et al.*⁷ measured the conductances of quaternary ammonium salts of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and ClO_4^- in 2-propanol at 25°. They found the

Fig. 1. (F.K.S.) plots for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in 2-propanol at 25°.

order of solvation (a^0) to be $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$ and the order of association, $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$, which is in agreement with the present results. Evans and Kay⁸ measured the conductance of quaternary ammonium salt of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- in water at 25°. They found the order of solvation (a^0) to be $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^-$, which again is in agreement with the present results.

The increase of K_A values with increasing size of anions for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate can be explained in the light of the U term in the equation⁹,

$$\ln K_A = \ln(4\pi N a^0 / 3000) + e^2 / a^0 D k T + U$$

where, $U = \Delta S/k - E_s/kT$

$\Delta S/k$ is the entropy/Boltzmann constant ratio which illustrates the probability of the orientation of solvent molecules around the free ions, and E_s/kT is an energy relationship which includes the energy of the solvent molecules with respect to the two free ions and to the pair which they can form. The values of U term of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate are given in Table 3. The result reveals that the value of U increases slightly from Cl^- to Br^- , i.e. the entropy term is more predominant than ion-dipole term, while it decreases slightly from Br^- to ClO_4^- , i.e. the ion-dipole interaction term (E_s/kT) is more predominant than the entropy term.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED VALUES OF K_2 AND U FOR ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN 2-PROPANOL AT 25°

Salt	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
Ac.Cl	640.37	54.12	7.51	2.14
Ac.Br	670.03	59.33	10.30	2.42
Ac.I	935.50	89.36	9.47	3.35
Ac.ClO ₄	1051.80	141.71	6.42	2.00

Finally, the solvent separated-ion pair model is applied¹⁰. In this model a multiple-step association occurs, i.e. solvent separated-ion pair can be illustrated in the following scheme :

The association constant is given by

$$K_A = K\Sigma = \frac{[C_{(\text{ion-pairs})}]}{[C_{(\text{acetylcholine})}][C_{\text{X}^-(\text{solvent})_n}]} = K_1(1 + K_2)$$

where, $K\Sigma = K_A$ is obtained from conductance measurements,

$$K_1 = 4\pi Na^{0.3}/3000 e^b$$

K_2 was thus calculated. The results compiled in Table 3, indicate that K_1 increases from Cl^- to ClO_4^- , i.e. the ion-pair prefers the more solvated form (case I) than the desolvated form (case II).

Experimental

2-Propanol, acetylcholine chloride, bromide, iodide and perchlorate was purified as reported elsewhere². The specific conductance for the purified 2-propanol was found to be $(5.443 \times 10^{-8}) \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The density of 2-propanol was determined using a 20 ml pycnometer at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$ and was found to be 0.78097 g/cm^3 . Its viscosity was measured at 25° using a modified Ubelöhde suspended level viscometer with a flow-time of 172.4 s for water. It was found to be 0.02079 P. The dielectric constant value was used as reported in literature⁷.

All solutions were prepared by weight reduced to vacuo. Salts were weighed by difference on

a microbalance which read to $\pm 0.1 \text{ mg}$. Dilution was carried out successively into the cell by siphoning the solvent by means of dispenser.

An Erlenmeyer cell with bright platinum electrodes was used. Its cell constant was calculated $(0.05443 \pm 0.43\% \text{ cm}^{-1})$ using the Lind-Zwolenik-Fouss¹¹ equation.

A Pye 11700 conductance bridge was used for measuring the resistance of the solution at 5 kc/s.

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